

Report for EOSCpilot Project: Mapping of WP3 Draft Recommendations to the Landscape: a brief discussion of some contemporary data policy recommendation sets

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1. Introduction

The current work of Work Package (WP) 3 of the European Open Science Cloud for Research Pilot Project (henceforth 'EOSCpilot') focuses on development of the policy landscape for the EOSC, and is taking place within a complex and fast-evolving landscape of other, related sets of policy recommendations. As such it was felt that examination of the key relationships between the EOSCpilot WP3 draft recommendations for Open Science and these other recommendations sets should be undertaken.

This document identifies some concurrent recommendation sets arising from the European open science and research data infrastructure landscape, and outlines some key relationships between these recommendation sets and the EOSCpilot WP3 policy work.

It is important to note that the EOSCpilot WP3 policy work, in issuing a set of recommendations, does not aim to cover the same ground as any other set of recommendations; the WP has a discrete focus - namely to support development of the EOSC policy environment from within the context of a preliminary pilot phase. Whilst the work of the WP attempts to address the concerns or requirements of the wider Open Science, Open Data and data infrastructure landscapes, it is worth noting that the way the proposed EOSC might best operate is the lens through which these issues are viewed. Our concern is to primarily identify whether there are any themes that emerge strongly from the current batch of recommendation sets, and also whether there are any contradictions between the EOSCpilot WP3 recommendations and any other sets.

We do not attend here to the relationships between the other recommendation sets: our focus is on the connections or contradictions between the EOSCpilot WP3 work, on the one hand, and the other named recommendation sets on the other.

The analysis supplied here for WP3 recommendations follows the numbering of the draft set of WP3 recommendations as published in Deliverable D3.3, as follows:

- Rec 1. Develop a Charter for Access to EOSC Infrastructures, Services and Other Resources
- Rec 2. Adopt the AARC framework for enabling an interoperable AAI infrastructure
- Rec 3. Adopt a minimum metadata schema and limited number of APIs to be considered as standard for services, infrastructures and other resources in the EOSC Service Catalogue
- Rec 4. Adopt and measure user acknowledgement of use of or contribution to research results of EOSC services, infrastructures and other resources
- Rec 5. Develop an Evaluation and Ranking of Openness Maturity of EOSC services, infrastructures and other resources
- Rec 6. Adopt a minimal set of standards for data/metadata and exchange protocols
- Rec 7. Reduce regulatory complexity for researchers
- Rec 8. Develop and adopt a European Open Science Concordat
- Rec 9. Encourage the development of an EOSC TDM (Text and Data mining) Policy Framework

- Rec 10. Develop principles for long-term data stewardship enabling curation, provenance and quality
- Rec 11. Use community accepted standards and conventions.
- Rec 12. Standardise costs types of Open Science (OA, RDM, Preservation, etc) at all levels
- Rec 13. Make DMPs a requirement and develop consistent (i.e. aligned) requirements for DMPs
- Rec 14. Encourage the use of unique and persistent digital identifiers
- Rec 15. Ensure that infrastructures, services and other resources supplied through the EOSC provide assurance, for example by developing accreditation or certification schemes
- Rec 16. Develop, support and promote an EOSC Skills and Capability Framework as a common reference point
- Rec 17. Coordinate Open Access and IPR reutilisation in a comprehensive and coherent IPR framework
- Rec 18. Have proper IPR documentation when releasing or accessing a research resource
- Rec 19. Clear IPRs before sharing them over e-Infrastructures/ Research Infrastructures
- Rec 20. Provide coherent and consistent IPR ownership policies
- Rec 21. Have a clear access and rights management regime
- Rec 22. Ensure that licensing policies accommodate different types of value production
- Rec 23. Introduce Open Access enforcement policies and mechanisms
- Rec 24. Devise and deploy open patent systems along the existing patent systems and support the use of open data for assessing the state of the art in a patent ecosystem.
- Rec 25. Adopt the recommendation of the OSPP Working Group on Rewards and embed Open Science in the evaluation of researchers at all stages of their career
- Rec 26. Promote and support Open Next Generation Metrics infrastructure
- Rec 27. Develop and operate Open Science Monitoring as an integral core service of EOSC
- Rec 28. Develop and maintain a machine-readable Open Science Registry for EOSC

These draft recommendations are the starting point for the current analysis. They have since been rearranged into four themes: Ethical, Open, Secure and Cost-effective, containing limited rewording and some additional material. This new, revised version of the WP3 recommendations took place after the current analysis was completed.

NB: Where possible and for clarity, the version of any recommendation set referred to in this report is specified as 'draft', 'revised' or 'final' as appropriate, but WP3 phrasing is consistently taken from the draft recommendation set as that was the most mature version of the text at the time of the full mapping exercise and is the basis on which comparison with the other recommendation sets was performed.

2. Some recommendation sets arising from concurrent international research data policy work

The WP3 draft policy recommendations are provided in section 1 above. At approximately the same time, three key sets of recommendations emerged from European Commission-supported work, which we consider in terms of their relevance to the work of WP3. In this section each recommendation set is named, its authorship outlined and its focus or scope described.

- a) "Prompting an EOSC in practice: Interim report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group [2017-2018] on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)"

Our acronym: HLEG2

Location and authorship: Draft recommendations were published at https://eosc-pilot.eu/sites/default/files/prompting_an_eosc_in_practice_eosc_hleg_interim_report.pdf. pp. 36-37. Subsequently, an unpublished revised version was circulated offline for comment whilst WP3 work was underway, which was incorporated here and somewhat complicated the task of mapping. A further, final version of the HLEG2 recommendation set was published on 21 Nov 2018 at <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>, after the current analysis was completed. This third and final version of the recommendation set once again revised the numbering and some wording. This group was chaired by Silvana Muscella of Trust-IT Services.

Structure and scope: The first version of this set of recommendations consists of 21 x top-down recommendations split into 3 x sections: Implementation; Engagement; and Steering. The revised and final published versions followed a similar progression in the layout of recommendations. These recommendations appear to be written for those who are members of the executive of the EOSC when it becomes operational, and those who support the EOSC executive to carry out their responsibilities. Thus, this group of recommendations is not focused on EOSC stakeholders in a broader sense, including users. Rather, this set of recommendations is for those setting up, advocating for, and running the EOSC - hence the structure of the three corresponding sections.

- b) "Turning FAIR data into reality: Final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data"

Our acronym: FDEG

Location and authorship: This report and action plan was published on 26 Nov 2018, after the majority of the development had already been done on the WP3 recommendations. The final publication is available here: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7769a148-f1f6-11e8-9982-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. The interim version is at <https://zenodo.org/record/1285290#.XAarZydRdE4>. The FDEG group was chaired by Simon Hodson of CODATA.

Structure and scope: This set of recommendations is explicitly for the use of all who are interested in the concept of findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable ("FAIR") data, as conceptualised in the FAIR Data Principles¹ and is not limited to stakeholders of the EOSC, or even those working in the European context. FAIR data is a global, region-agnostic concept and as such this set of recommendations responds to that global positioning. The draft version provided a massive set of 103 x recommendations split across 34 topics or thematic clusters. Of these, only one topic (no. 34, p. 20), containing two recs, was written to be directly relevant to the EOSC, although of course meaning could be extrapolated from some other recommendations by EOSC

¹ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

stakeholders where required. However it is not assumed in our mapping that the “FAIR data ecosystem” referred to in these recommendations is concomitant with the proposed EOSC. P. 21 of the FDEG recommendations provides more information on the relationship between the FDEG recs and plans for the proposed EOSC, namely that the FDEG recs are engaging with a larger, global vision and this should guide thinking on the EOSC.

- c) EC Open Science Policy Platform recommendations - otherwise known as the “integrated advice of the Open Science Policy Platform on 8 prioritised Open Science ambitions”²

Our acronym: OSPP

Location and authorship: These recommendations are available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/integrated_advice_opspp_recommendations.pdf. These were published earlier than all the other sets, on 23 April 2018 under the group’s first mandate. Membership of the group is listed at https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/ospp_nominated_members.pdf. The group is currently in its second mandate, and the current chair is Dr Eva Méndez of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Structure and scope: These recommendations consist of 5 x 'General' recommendations, plus a recommendation set for each of the 8 x ambitions for Open Science as defined by the European Open Science Agenda. Several recommendations for each ambition are provided, as set out below:

A. Rewards and Incentives (recs x 4)
B. Research indicators and Next-Generation Metrics (recs x 4)
C. Future of Scholarly Comms (recs x 4)
D. EOSC (recs x 3)
E. FAIR data (recs x 3)
F. Research Integrity (recs x 4)
G. Skills and Education (recs x 2)
H. Citizen Science (recs x 4)

The aim of the group’s work is to “provide advice about the development and implementation of Open science policy in Europe” - as such, these recommendations need not restrict themselves to data-related issues. The 5 x 'General' recommendations are dense and compound, often comprising a series of related but separate actionable points in the one 'recommendation'. The recommendations under each of the 8 x ambitions are more discrete and actionable. It is worth emphasising that only one section is intended to be directly relevant to the EOSC. However, other sections have also been considered where relevant to the EOSC pilot recommendations.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform>

3. Thematic confluence across recommendation sets

Given the shared concerns of many of the initiatives included here, it is unsurprising that there is a certain amount of thematic confluence between the WP3 draft recommendations for policy and the issues addressed by the recommendations produced by HLEG2, FDEG and OSPP.

We have found three levels of confluence between WP3 recommendations and the other sets considered. These are as follows:

- **Strong correlation:** that the other recommendation sets all include a recommendation which is considered to correspond with a specific WP3 recommendation.
- **Moderate correlation:** that there is at least one firm example of the specified WP3 recommendation being confluent with a recommendation from one of the other recommendation sets.
- **Weak (but existing) correlation:** that, upon reflection, the specified WP3 recommendation may be broadly or arguably confluent with at least one other recommendation from HLEG2, FDEG or OSPP.
- For remaining recommendations, the analysis has found **no meaningful correlation**. These are analysed together in section 4, below.

a. Strong thematic correlation

Of the twenty-eight draft WP3 policy recommendations, two are considered here to be clearly echoed across all other recommendation sets. The first of these is WP3 recommendation 11 (draft) / OS4.1 (revised): 'Use community accepted standards and conventions'. The key ideas in this recommendation appear in other related recommendations as follows:

- HLEG2: Rec I-4 (interim I-2) argues for interoperability standards to 'be based on existing open standards'. Rec I-9 (interim I-6) argues for standards within EOSC for information encoding, and protocols for data sharing and publication, to be based on 'international standards'. In our mapping we have taken 'community-accepted' to be a reasonable synonym for 'existing open standards' and 'international standards', on the basis that the existing and international standards which are most likely to be usefully deployed in the EOSC environment are only those which are already accepted by the community.
- FDEG: Rec 8.1 stipulates, 'Efforts should be made to identify information and practices that apply across research communities and articulate these in common standards that provide a baseline for FAIR.' In this mapping, again a necessary process of interpretation allows us to align 'common' with 'community accepted' standards, for the reasons stated above, and particularly due to the emphasis in the FDEG recommendation on understanding existing community practices. The FDEG report strengthens this position with a general statement that EOSC policy development should be guided by the broader FDEG recs to ensure EOSC services are interoperable with those of other international initiatives beyond Europe (see p. 21 of draft).
- OSPP: The second stipulation of the section, 'Research Integrity' requires that "All published research outputs should be reported according to recognised community standards where they exist." This indicates that OSPP too is keen to systematise working with standards that already have traction in a given research community.

- To be clear, there is no attempt in this WP3 recommendation to stipulate or recommend any particular standards - the spirit of this WP3 recommendation is that where standards are to be used, it is important that these already have community acceptance and are not seen as being imposed by the EOSC regardless of existing community practice.

The second WP3 recommendation with particularly strong reinforcement from other recommendation sets is recommendation 25 (draft) / OS6 (revised) 'Adopt the recommendation of the OSPP Working Group on Rewards and embed Open Science in the evaluation of researchers at all stages of their career'. It is to be welcomed that all recommendation sets recognise to some extent the importance of re-thinking the researcher reward system, particularly where this includes the recognition of Open science and/or data sharing practices. These ideas are echoed in other recommendation sets at the following points:

- HLEG2: recommendation E-1 (final) states, 'create career-enhancing incentives for researchers who open the science ... they produce', which speaks clearly to our shared concern with reward structures for Open science that enhance career progression at all stages.
- FDEG: This theme is touched on several times in the FDEG report. Firstly, recommendation 14.3 (draft) / action 6.3 (revised) reads, 'Evidence of past practice in support of FAIR data should be included in assessments of research contribution. Such evidence should be required in grant proposals (for both research and infrastructure investments), for career advancement, for publication and conference contributions, and other evaluation schemes.' This is highly relevant if Open Science is seen as part of "FAIR data" practice.
- OSPP: In 'Rewards and Incentives', the first bullet states, "Funders, research institutions and other evaluators of researchers should actively develop / adjust evaluation practices and routines to give extra credit to individuals, groups and projects who integrate Open Science within their research practices." The positioning of this recommendation as the first one of the entire set of prioritised recommendations for the eight ambitions of Open Science suggests the importance with which this aim is regarded.

b. Moderate thematic correlation

For eight WP3 recommendations, we can see moderate support which is here understood to include at least one directly-related recommendation in another recommendation set. There may additionally be some other recommendations that are potentially confluent. The first of the moderately-supported recommendations is number 6 (draft) / OS4.1 (revised): 'Adopt a minimal set of standards for data/metadata and exchange protocols'.

- HLEG2: This is echoed in rec I-9 (draft I-6) to a certain extent, but this does not specifically include metadata, and keeping the set 'minimal' is not emphasised. Also, the EOSCpilot recommendation reads as a more technical standard set, whereas the HLEG2 recommendation (draft text: 'Adopt EOSC standards – from international standards - for information encoding and for protocols for data sharing and publication to implement FAIR principles over data and services in a complete & efficient way. And vice versa, offer open EOSC standards to international standardisation bodies') reads as more socio-technical.
- FDEG: Similar ideas are sought by recommendation 25.2 (draft): 'Metadata standards should be adopted and used consistently in order to enable machines to discover,

assess and utilise data at scale.’ Again, however, ‘minimal’ is not a stated consideration here.

- OSPP: No direct echoing, but 2.1.2 of ‘General recommendations’ states: ‘Ensure the scholarly infrastructure in Europe is highly interoperable to enable the simple and open sharing of metadata between systems, disciplines and countries...’, echoing the importance of common approaches to metadata.

The second is recommendation 9 (draft) / OS3.6 (revised), ‘Encourage the development of an EOSC TDM (Text and Data mining) Policy Framework’.

- HLEG2: Not explicitly addressed.
- FDEG: Not explicitly addressed.
- OSPP: The first point under section, ‘Future of Scholarly Communication’ specifies: "All published research outputs from public funding in Europe must be made public in a way that ensures both immediate open access and full text and data mining rights of that content ...". So this is not precisely encouragement of a specific policy framework for TDM alone, but it can be interpreted as a general encouragement for TDM to be included in policy.

The third is recommendation 12 (draft) / OS4.3 (revised) : ‘Standardise costs types of Open Science (OA, RDM, Preservation, etc) at all levels’.

- HLEG2: Not explicitly addressed.
- FDEG: Recommendation 32 (draft) advises that ‘Research funders should require data management costs to be considered and included in grant applications, where relevant. To support this, detailed guidelines and worked examples of eligible costs for FAIR data should be provided.’ The recommendation then gives more specification for transparency of costing. This does not explicitly demand standardisation, but it does tackle issues around making costs transparent and providing exemplar costings, which are practical actions likely to result in more standardisation of costs for RDM and Open science.
- OSPP: Not explicitly addressed.

The fourth is recommendation number 13 (draft) / OS4.4 (revised): ‘Make DMPs a requirement and develop consistent (i.e. aligned) requirements for DMPs.’

- HLEG2: Not explicitly addressed.
- FDEG: Group 21 (draft) heavily implies DMPs to be mandated, and information from DMPs to be i) FAIR in itself and ii) reused in CRIS and other systems. Recommendation 5 (final) is clear: ‘Ensure data management via DMPs’; and contains four supporting actions.
- OSPP: In section ‘FAIR Data’, the second recommendation clearly proposes ‘Output management plans (OMPs) including data management plans (DMPs) should be mandatory for all research projects’.

The fifth is recommendation 14 (draft) / OS4.2 (revised): ‘Encourage the use of unique and persistent digital identifiers’.

- HLEG2: Possibly implied within recommendations on use of existing standards and protocols, as DOI - for example - is a persistent identifier and also an ISO standard. However, this EOSC pilot recommendation doesn't specify DOIs by name, and DOIs are also not named in the HLEG recs. In addition, I-6 (draft) argues for adoption of ‘protocols for data ... publication’ based on international standards. I-13 (revised)

mentions a need for 'coherent identification and referencing of research entities and resources' which may imply the use of persistent digital identifiers for these resources. The final version of the HLEG recommendation set mentions identifiers in passing during discussion of the proposed minimum viable ecosystem but stops short of specifically recommending their use.

- FDEG: Recommendation 3.1 (draft) specifies that 'Universal use of appropriate PIDs [persistent identifiers] needs to be facilitated and implemented'. The issue continues through to the final report where recommendation 3: 'Develop components of a FAIR ecosystem' specifies a need for digital object identifiers as a native element of the proposed model for 'FAIR data objects'.
- OSPP: Recommendation 2.1.2 specifies: "This will need all actors to require the use of standardised, unique persistent identifiers for researchers and outputs..." In addition, section 'Research Indicators and Next-Generation Metrics', recommendation 3 adds: "All researchers need to be identified through an ORCID ID."

The sixth is recommendation 15 (draft) / OS2.5 (revised): 'Ensure that infrastructures, services and other resources supplied through the EOSC provide assurance, for example by developing accreditation or certification schemes'.

- HLEG2: Recommendation I-5 (revised) proposes Quality of Service standard(s) 'to develop a trustable ecosystem'. Additionally, recommendation I-10 (revised) promotes 'development of services as independent, interoperable and exchangeable building blocks to foster the future accreditation of innovative and / or efficient alternatives'.
- FDEG: The draft recommendation 13.3 specifies, 'Accreditation should be developed for training and qualifications for these [data science and data stewardship] roles.' Also, the 'FAIR metrics text' of p. 18 (draft) is clear that CoreTrustSeal is the recognised accreditation scheme for repository quality assurance, and that "new accreditation schemes are needed" for other parts of the FAIR data ecosystem, e.g. "identifier services, standards and vocabularies".
- OSPP: In the section 'EOSC', recommendation 1 and recommendation 2 mention the trustworthiness of EOSC. Does 'assurance' here mean trustworthiness? OSPP recommendation 1 aims for EOSC governance to happen in such a way that 'it has the trust and confidence of all stakeholders..'; rec. 2 notes the need for a long-term baseline funding commitment for the EOSC 'to become trustworthy'.

The seventh is recommendation 23 (draft) / OS3.4 (revised): 'Introduce Open Access enforcement policies and mechanisms', which in the revised version is presented in the context of a proposed IPR framework.

- HLEG2: This is arguably implied by other recommendations on e.g. protocols for data publication in rec I-6 (draft), and in engagement with national and international frameworks in rec E-3 (draft). It is also arguably implied by I-1 (draft): 'The EOSC should ... do whatever it takes to increase the availability and volume of quality and user friendly scientific information online.'
- FDEG: Not explicitly addressed. The FDEG work takes Open Access for granted as a part of the scholarly landscape, rather than as a subject for its direct attention.
- OSPP: In the section, 'Future of Scholarly Communication', recommendation 1 states: 'All published research outputs from public funding in Europe must be made public in a way that ensures both immediate open access and full text and data mining rights of that content ...'. Further, recommendation 2 of the same section adds, 'Each member state

... must develop policies to guarantee compliance with the EU OA mandate, including both incentives and enforcement, by 2020.'

Lastly, the eighth of the moderately-supported recommendations is number 26 (draft) / OS7.1 (revised) : 'Promote and support Open Next Generation Metrics infrastructure'.

- HLEG2: This aim is arguably implied by recommendation E-1 (draft), addressing the creation of career-enhancing incentives for Open science activity.
- FDEG: Recommendation 31 (draft) / 26 (final) urges support for 'data citation and next generation metrics'.
- OSPP: This set contains an entire section on the topic of 'Research Indicators and Next Generation Metrics', containing four complex supporting recommendations.
- Across this group of recommendation sets there is little in the way of definition of what constitutes a 'next generation metric', but the FDEG comes the closest by discussing such metrics as works in progress and states 'a variety of ways of assessing influence and impact should be incorporated' in the development of these metrics (recommendation 26) (final).

c. Weak (but existing) thematic correlation

These WP3 recommendations have weak, but existing, thematic correlation with the other recommendation sets. This occurs where we have concluded that the phrasing from other recommendation sets may possibly imply a connection. This is likely to be the case in the six following draft WP3 recommendations, which indicates these are issues that are acknowledged by at least one other recommendation set, but do not appear to be of sufficient importance to be directly and unambiguously addressed in their recommendations.

The first of the weakly-echoed WP3 recommendations is number 1 (draft) / OS2 (revised): 'Develop a Charter for Access to EOSC Infrastructures, Services and Other Resources'.

- HLEG2: An access charter or similar is not specified, but may be implied by rec. I-10 (draft) / I-13 (final): 'Simplify early (beta) participation in the EOSC by potential data providers, service providers, and underlying infrastructure providers, by relaxing initial constraints but without relaxing quality standards for data and services.'
- FDEG: A charter for access to the EOSC is not included, but is possibly implied by recommendation 34 (draft), "The Rules of Engagement for EOSC must be broadly-defined and open to enable all existing service providers to address the criteria and be part of the European network', but only if a Charter for Access can be seen as equivalent to Rules of Engagement. This recommendation does not seem to have survived into the final version of the report, but the existence of EOSC 'rules of engagement' are mentioned in passing as part of the landscape (final, p. 54).
- OSPP: Not explicitly addressed.

Secondly, recommendation 4 (draft) / OS2.3 (revised). 'Adopt and measure user acknowledgement of use of or contribution to research results of EOSC services, infrastructures and other resources' - this recommendation is tricky to map as it is unclear precisely what this phrasing includes. For example, it doesn't make sense to 'adopt ... user acknowledgement'. But if this WP3 recommendation is interpreted generally as 'pay attention to / measure what users do and what they acknowledge the EOSC as being useful for', there is possible link to the following recommendations from HLEG2:

- E-4 (draft) / E-5 (revised): "To stimulate the demand side of the EOSC, ensure establishment of dedicated funding for demonstration of the EOSC at EU level that would include researchers and their infrastructure providers e.g. EOSC in practice stories, cross-disciplinary success of EOSC."
- The concept of training and supporting data experts in use, in recommendation I-12 (draft) / I-16 (revised), may connect - presumably part of understanding user needs is paying attention to what users acknowledge they use EOSC for.
- Rec E-I may also connect, because user acknowledgement of use of EOSC is presumably part of understanding who the researchers are in E-1 that should receive the 'career-enhancing incentives'.
- Also possibly new recommendation I-18 (revised) (monitoring data access and reuse to demonstrate impact)
- I-2 (revised) also argues for KPIs to demonstrate value brought by EOSC - this may be related in practice.

Thirdly, recommendation 28 (draft) / OS7.2 (revised) advises: 'Develop and maintain a machine-readable Open Science Registry for EOSC'.

- HLEG2: Not explicitly addressed.
- FDEG: Implied by 15.4 (draft) / 17.3 (final): Policies should be versioned, indexed and semantically annotated in a policy registry. However, the development and maintenance is not advocated for here as a recommended activity, and 'machine-readable' is also not specified here.
- OSPP: Again, the deposit but not the development and maintenance is implied in section 'Future of Scholarly Communication', recommendation 1: 'Venues used for the publication of research outputs must ensure machine-readable information on their Open Science policies.'

The fourth and fifth draft recommendations classified here are recommendation 18 (draft), 'Have proper IPR documentation when releasing or accessing a research resource', and recommendation 19 (draft), 'Clear IPRs before sharing them over e-Infrastructures/ Research Infrastructures' which have both been rephrased into OS3.1 (revised): 'Ensure that research resources have IPR clearance and are fully and clearly documented in terms of IPR before being shared over EOSC'.

- HLEG2: This seems broadly in line with the HLEG2 high-level approach to licensing issues, advocating for a 'short list' of licenses that would 'meet the needs of all' (7b, final).
- FDEG: The FDEG's vision of a FAIR data object involves the usage licence to be included in metadata.
- OSPP: The section, 'Future of Scholarly Communication', point 3, requires a licence for the use of the underpinning dataset to be deposited with every publication.

The sixth rephrased WP3 recommendation is number 20 (draft): 'Provide coherent and consistent IPR ownership policies' which is now rephrased in OS3.2 (revised): 'Each organisation participating in the EOSC should develop and require adherence to a set of explicit, coherent, consistent and machine readable IPR ownership and licensing policies'. OS3.2 now functions as a way of supporting OS3 ('Encourage open access to and reutilisation of research outputs by providing a comprehensive and coherent IPR framework') by requiring participants to adhere to the framework specified in OS3. This is cohesive with HLEG2's dream of a licensing scheme that 'meets the needs of all', the FDEG's proposed structure for a FAIR

data object including licence in its metadata, and the OSPP recommendation for a license for reuse to be available with every dataset underpinning publication. None of these recommendations explicitly require the development requested here but the ambition is broadly shared.

Due to the rewriting of draft recommendations 18 and 20, they continue to appear in the supporting figures as ‘not correlated’ to the other recommendation sets, which is where they were coded prior to their rewriting for subsequent versions.

4. Difference in coverage between WP3 recommendations and other recommendation sets

There are some differences in thematic coverage between the recommendations set out by WP3 and the other sets of recommendations discussed here. As discussed above, this is not necessarily a problem: the initiatives and their various foci have always been different and to a certain extent they speak to different audiences; there is no need for them to present the same conclusions. However it is of interest to us if there are any specific contradictions which clearly and unambiguously emerge from these sets of recommendations.

Whilst we have not identified any specific, explicit, simple contradictions between the WP3 recommendations and those other recommendation sets examined in this analysis, there are two examples where approaches to a topic are markedly - and importantly - divergent.

- Recommendation 10 (draft) / OS4.5 (revised). ‘Develop principles for long-term data stewardship enabling curation, provenance and quality’ - the FDEG conceptualises the skills for data as existing in two categories: data science, and data stewardship. However, FDEG work draws on the existence of many principles already in place for the demands of long-term data stewardship which already exist in the digital preservation, digital curation and archive communities and explicitly refers to the value of “established archival principles” (recommendation 19, final). As such, it does not recommend development of new versions of these principles and indeed argues that long-term data stewardship should be understood as a pre-existing fundamental function for FAIR data which should be recognised, incorporated and professionalised. OSPP similarly argues for the value of development of training materials for, inter alia, data stewards, and again does not recommend (re)creation of a new set of principles here.
- Recommendation 16 (draft) / OS5 (revised). ‘Develop, support and promote an EOSC Skills and Capability Framework as a common reference point’. The other recommendation sets recognise the need for skills provision, but none recommend the building of a new framework. As with WP3 recommendation 10 (draft) / OS4.5 (revised), the other recommendation sets recognise the work that already exists in this area and do not propose (re)creation of a new framework, but rather that the existing efforts that show genuine value in the community are brought together, supported and developed. The FDEG vision is that a “foundational” level of competence in data skills is embedded in undergraduate and postgraduate tertiary education, independently of any particular initiative. FDEG recommendation 11 specifically supports the deployment of existing curriculum frameworks for data science and data stewardship. This recommendation and recommendation 10 (draft) / OS4.5 (revised) are possibly the closest the other

recommendation sets come to contradicting the probable intent of WP3 recommendations.

These two recommendations aside, there is a high degree of overall cohesion on most other points. However, this does not mean that contradictory actions cannot arise. At their heart, recommendations all attempt to balance an aspiration with a tractable action. This balancing act invariably incorporates room for individuals to interpret a given recommendation - from any set - in a way that may be different from the way another individual would do so. Doubtlessly, there will be contradictory aims and objectives sought by stakeholders when attempting to operationalise these sets of recommendations. An obvious example of an area of likely conflict is the role of commercial, profit-focused actors as they operate in the landscape of the EOSC. The EOSC is philosophically based upon the principles of Open knowledge, Open data and Open science which explicitly aim to remove paywalls to knowledge infrastructures in order to benefit society. In all recommendation sets, authors have attempted to encourage and to a certain extent protect the interests of Open science and Open data, whilst still allowing powerful commercial actors room to maneuver and monetise the space. Another difficult balancing act attempted in many recommendation sets is to present their recommendation sets as concise, clear and actionable, whilst also attempting to be comprehensive in tackling all the policy points that must be addressed to comply with legal requirements, avoid criticism from stakeholders and support the requirements of varied audiences of researchers from many different disciplines, infrastructure providers, and policy makers. In short, it is impossible to rule out the potential for contradictions in policy or practice to arise from those attempting in good faith to work in line with any of the recommendations in our analysis.

It is more tractable to examine the extent to which recommendation sets do or do not cover the same topics, or whether there are meaningful differences in stated attitudes to the same topic.

Twelve of the twenty-eight WP3 draft recommendations are not substantially echoed in recommendation sets produced by HLEG2, FDEG or OSPP. This indicates that a slight majority - sixteen - of the draft WP3 recommendations can be strongly, moderately or weakly tied to at least one other recommendation produced by HLEG2, FDEG or OSPP but a large minority cannot. What does this divergence from other current recommendation sets mean?

The first obvious point is that the scope of WP3 appears to have varied in some areas from that of the other recommendation sets, all of which are highly valuable contributions to the current research data landscape. WP3 is part of the EOSCpilot project and is concerned with development of policy for the EOSC. As such, it is influenced by the findings of other WPs within the project as well as by external input. Accordingly, the WP differs from the FDEG and OSPP, both of which are tasked with the wider landscapes of FAIR data and Open science respectively. The remaining recommendation set, HLEG2, is also focused on the EOSC and builds on the earlier HLEG1 report and the FDEG and OSPP recommendations to attempt a cohesive response. The HLEG2 has ultimately come up with 21 Implementation recommendations including nine labelled for the EOSC, as well as five Engagement and six Steering recommendations. In this way, the HLEG2 report can be understood as sitting halfway between the outward-facing, internationally-applicable concerns of FDEG and OSPP, and the work of WP3 which takes place within the context of the EOSCpilot project. WP3 is the only initiative here entirely focused on producing recommendations for the EOSC policy environment, rather than its surrounding context. This does not mean that WP3 recommendations are not engaged with the wider landscape; in fact, external interoperability of

principles, technical infrastructure and policy decisions constitute a strong theme throughout the revised WP3 recommendation set. But the focus of the WP is distinct from the foci of the other sets discussed here.

Care was taken to gather feedback on the draft WP3 recommendations through a cohort of surveys and several workshops during 2018. On that basis, the WP understands the WP3 policy recommendation set as offering something distinct to its potential user community. The nature of that distinct offering can be understood by examining the scope of the unmatched recommendations, aside from those two highly divergent recommendations discussed above. The remaining ten are listed below:

- Recommendation 2 (draft) / OS2.1 (revised): 'Adopt the AARC framework for enabling an interoperable AAI infrastructure' - this topic was not addressed in earlier versions of HLEG2 but is now mentioned on p. 19 (final) in a discussion section about the work of the AARC2 project (2017-19). However there is no explicit recommendation either there or in other sets.
- Recommendation 3 (draft) / OS2.2 (revised): 'Adopt a minimum metadata schema and limited number of APIs to be considered as standard for services, infrastructures and other resources in the EOSC Service Catalogue' - there is no mention in HLEG2 draft recommendations, but this topic emerges in section 6.2, challenge 1: 'it is fundamental to build services on open standards APIs and protocols.' However this is not in the recommendation set and there is no mention of minimum metadata standards. The FDEG report identifies 'discovery metadata' as one element of 'the basic minimum standard' for a FAIR data ecosystem, but does not tackle this in their recommendation set. OSPP again positions open metadata development as important and metadata as a fundamental and necessary basic element of a data ecosystem but there is no recommendation for a minimum set of metadata or APIs.
- Recommendation 5 (draft) / OS2.4 (revised): 'Develop an Evaluation and Ranking of Openness Maturity of EOSC services, infrastructures and other resources' - it is clear that HLEG2 puts Open at the core of the envisaged EOSC, but there is no indication of that open-ness being either defined or measured. The FDEG is keen to bring about a FAIRness maturity model, but there is no specific support for Openness maturity. OSPP does not tackle this idea.
- Recommendation 7 (draft) / does not appear in revised version: 'Reduce regulatory complexity for researchers' - this can be compared with HLEG2 recommendation I-10 which specifies simplification of early participation in EOSC rather than simplification of regulatory environment per se. The interim FDEG report stressed harmonisation of policy rather than reduction of regulatory complexity, see e.g. 2.1 and 15.2. OSPP does not address the issue.
- Recommendation 8 (draft): 'Develop and adopt a European Open Science Concordat' has been rephrased in OS4 as '... a European Open Science Code of Conduct' (revised). Both FDEG and OSPP refer to existing codes for research practice and / or data but neither recommend the development of a new code. OSPP 2.1.1 recommends "Appoint national coordinators and task forces for the implementation of Open Science ... to ensure the coordinated action required for tangible change towards an open

science approach." This may amount to a European OS concordat or code of conduct but this is not specified. In addition, the first recommendation in the 'EOSC' section argues for a cohesive EC-wide approach which again might imply the value of such a code.

- Recommendation 17 (draft) / OS3 (revised): 'Coordinate Open Access and IPR reutilisation in a comprehensive and coherent IPR framework' - HLEG2 takes a very high level approach to licensing issues, advocating for a 'short list' of licenses that would 'meet the needs of all' (7b, final). The FDEG's vision of a FAIR data object involves the usage licence to be included in metadata. OSPP's section, 'Future of Scholarly Communication', point 3, requires a licence for the use of the underpinning dataset to be deposited with every publication. In all three cases, the recommendations, whilst acknowledging the importance of licensing, appears to differ from the detail required by the WP3 vision of a 'comprehensive and coherent framework'.
- Recommendation 21 (draft) / subsumed into OS3 (revised): 'Have a clear access and rights management regime'. See Recommendation 17, above, for discussion of the treatment of IPR across the recommendation sets.
- Recommendation 22 (draft) / OS3.3 (revised): 'Ensure that licensing policies accommodate different types of value production' - all sets address the licensing issue in one way or another, but the key point here is the variety of value types conceptualised. This is not addressed by HLEG2 or OSPP. The FDEG argues for a wider definition of value for research outputs but recommendations do not directly tie this to licensing policies.
- Recommendation 24 (draft) / OS3.5 (revised): 'Devise and deploy open patent systems along the existing patent systems and support the use of open data for assessing the state of the art in a patent ecosystem.' - this issue is not addressed by the other recommendation sets.
- Recommendation 27 (draft) / subsumed into the discussion of OS7 (revised): 'Develop and operate Open Science Monitoring as an integral core service of EOSC'. In HLEG2, this might possibly be implied by E-1, 'Create career-enhancing incentives for researchers who open the science that they produce [...] and make the EOSC a portal to those incentives', but is not directly stated. Possibly implied by FDEG point 30 (interim), which requires monitoring of FAIR to "track how the landscape matures" as well as for use in the informing and iteration of data policy, but again this is supposition. OSPP doesn't directly address this idea.

5. Conclusions

It is important to note that the two universally-supported recommendations address respectful support for community-supported standards; and meaningful recognition for researchers for their open science activities including data sharing. In both cases, these recommendations thus demonstrate respect and support for existing research practice and show that researchers and their existing practices are seen by all initiatives as the top priority stakeholder for moving Open science forward.

In the analysis of moderately-supported recommendations, we often see a mixture of strengths of phrasing for each topic. Examples of this include WP3 recommendation 14 (draft) / OS4.2 (revised), 'Encourage the use of unique and persistent digital identifiers'. All sets mentioned this should happen but there is greater and lesser strength of emphasis from different sets.

Sometimes the discussion varied around *how* an issue should be tackled rather than *whether* it should be. For example, in discussion of a minimal set of standards for metadata and exchange protocols, the shading of meaning is around the existence of such standards rather than whether it was important to create a shared minimal set or not.

In some cases, it is interesting to note that whilst a given WP3 recommendation is strongly echoed in one or possibly two other recommendation sets, there are some other sets that do not address the given issue. This is one of the most interesting aspects of this analysis as we see a clear division between those who, like WP3, think the issue is important in contrast with those who do not address it at all. There are two examples here: the development of a TDM policy framework is only addressed by WP3 and the OSPP; and costs typology and standardisation is only covered by WP3 and the FDEG. But in most cases, the moderately-supported recommendations have echoes in all other sets to some extent or another.

In considering the WP3 draft recommendations that are not directly echoed by another recommendation set, it is worth noting that the topic in several such WP3 recommendations is in fact included in the discussion sections of other recommendation sets. This indicates that other initiatives have also considered the topic an appropriate part of the ecosystem they are examining or proposing, but that they have stopped short of declaring a dedicated recommendation on the topic. This is confluent with the earlier discussion of the difference in focus for WP3 from the other recommendation-creating initiatives: the nuts and bolts of operationalising the EOSC are rightly more worthy of being directly addressed in the WP3 recommendation set.

In some instances - for example, the adoption of the AARC framework - it is recognised elsewhere that this project work is underway and likely to be adopted but this is indicated in a discussion passage. This may be an example where the WP3 work has gone to a higher level of specification of detail than other recommendation sets, for the reasons already discussed, and also because several WP3 recommendations - including WP3 draft recommendation 2 on adoption of the AARC framework - were written in support of the findings of some other WPs of the EOSCpilot project.

Overall this analysis shows a high level of cohesion between the WP3 recommendations and all other recommendation sets examined, with half of the draft set of WP3 recommendations being to some degree echoed by other recommendations. The difference in detail and scope can largely be understood as appropriate to the difference in focus for these various recommendation-producing initiatives.